

ETHNOGRAPHIC EXPRESSIONS OF CEREMONIES IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES

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Abstract. *Ethnographic units are diverse, and studying, researching, and classifying them allow for a deeper scientific analysis and interpretation of ethnographic terms. This classification categorizes people based on their culture, history, and traditions, a subject explored by many linguists and cultural scholars. In Uzbek linguistics, D. Khudoyberganova's work "Ethnographic Language Units" laid the groundwork for this field, while N.M. Shansky's research marked a significant contribution to world linguistics, classifying ethnographic units into three groups: historical ethnografisms (representing past management systems and social strata), cultural ethnografisms (reflecting lifestyle and customs), and social ethnografisms (indicating social ties and stratification). In the 1970s and 1980s, V. Superanskaya and E.M. Vereshchagin introduced a linguocultural approach that examined not only the vocabulary but also the cultural and historical contexts of these units, emphasizing their national characteristics. These studies highlight the role of ethnographic units in national culture, their significance in social life, and their influence on society through traditional rituals, such as Uzbek wedding ceremonies.*

Keywords: *ethnographic units, uzbek wedding rituals, bridal dowry (or wedding gifts), condolences and sympathy, cultural traditions, historical ethnographic units, functional ethnographic unit, geographical ethnographic unit, ethnographic classification.*

INTRODUCTION

Ethnographisms are different, and the process of their study, research and classification makes it possible to deepen the scientific analysis of ethnographic terms, to correctly interpret them. The study and classification of ethnographic terms involve organizing them according to their bonds with culture, history, and national traditions, an area that has been explored by various linguists and cultural scholars. Specifically, in Uzbek linguistics, the foundational scientific work on this topic is presented in D. Khudoyberganova's book "Ethnographic Linguistic Units".

In the context of global linguistics, the first classification efforts were made through the research of Russian linguist N.M. Shanskiy, marking an important milestone in the linguistic foundation of ethnographic term classification. Shanskiy explored the strong connection between ethnographic units and cultural-historical life, presented them as lexical items, and categorized them into the following three groups:

- historical ethnographies are the units which represent the historical system of governance and social interactions of past eras. For example, *podshoh, mirshab, knyaz, ritsar*;
- cultural ethnographies are the units that related to the way of life, customs and rituals of people. For example, *to'y, ma'raka, hayit, pasxa, uloq, ko'pkari, english breakfast*;
- social ethnographies – reflect the social relations, stratification of people. For example, *boylar, dehqonlar, ziyolilar, bog'bonlar, knyazlar, gersoglar, baronlar*, etc [1].

In the 1970s and 1980s, in their research on the classification of ethnographic units, A.V. Superanskaya and E.M. Vereshchagin proposed classifying ethnographic terms based on a linguocultural approach, where ethnographic linguistic units were described not only in terms of vocabulary but also in cultural and historical contexts. In these studies, special attention was given to the national characteristics preserved by ethnographic terms, and they were described as linguistic units that reveal the historical, geographical, and cultural uniqueness of a particular people. For example, the Uzbek tradition of *a cradle celebration (beshik to'yi)* is not just a family celebration related to the birth of a child, but also holds significant importance as a traditional cultural practice that reflects the connection between society and family [2].

In particular, Vereshchagin notes the importance of communicative-ethnographic units in this regard, analyzing their place in international cultural relations [3].

Superanskaya's "Obshaya teoriya imeni sobstvennogo", published in 1976, proposes the study of ethnographic units associated with national culture and geography in connection with national characteristics, place names and historical events associated with them: *geographical, cultural-ethnographic units, historical ethnographisms and ethnographic units related to tradition and crafts* [4]. She offers the following classification of ethnographisms:

1. Geographical-ethnographisms reflect the habitat, climatic conditions and geographical features of people. For example:

In Uzbek: *Farg'ona vodiysi, Chimyon tog'lari, Qizilquum, Mirzacho'l.*

In Russian: *Волга, Сибирская тайга, Уральские пещера.*

In Turkish: *Kapadokya, Boğaz köprüsü, Toros dağları.*

In English: *Niagara Falls (sharshara), Grand Canyon, Sahara Desert.*

These units, representing the name of the geographical area, embody the culture and geographical landscape of the people. Moreover, such words as *Samarqand noni, Buxoro ipak matosi, Xorazm lazgisi, Qo'qon do'ppisi* indicate not only the type of product, but also the specific values and habits of those regions.

2. Cultural-ethnographic units study the role of ethnographers in the cultural life of the people and what function they perform. For example:

In Uzbek: *Beshik to'yi, kelin salom, nikoh to'yi, chilla, Qurbon hayiti;*

In Russian: *Крестини (ceremony of bathing a child), Пасха, рождество, именины;*

In Turkish: *Sünnet düğünü, mevlüt, düğün;*

In English: *Thanksgiving, Baby shower, Wedding reception, Bonfire Night, New Year's Eve.*

3. Historical ethnographisms include specific place names and specific historical events associated with them.

In Uzbek: *Oq Saroy, Ulug'bek rasadxonasi, G'alab bog'i;*

In Russian: *Красная площадь, Эрмитаж, Царь-колокол;*

In Turkish: *Topkapı Sarayı, Çanakkale, Anıtkabir*

In English: *Stonehenge, Tower of London, Westminster Abbey.*

4. Ethnographic units related to tradition and crafts are ethnographisms related to national craft items and products.

In Uzbek: *beshik, adras, atlas, Chust pichog'i;*

In Russian: *самовар, гжельская керамика, хохлома;*

In Turkish: *hereke halısı, baklava, Çini (type of pottery art);*

In English: *Scottish Tartan, Wedgwood porcelain, Morris wallpaper.*

We found it expedient, based on the features of the application of ethnographisms, to classify them into types of historical-ethnographisms (*sarhadchi, mingboshi, ellikboshi, darvozabon*); dialectal-ethnographisms (*zirgacha – donkey, mastoba- mastava*) and modern-ethnographisms (*bloger, tik toker, freelancer*).

The culture of any nation cannot be imagined without weddings and mourning ceremonies. In particular, Uzbek wedding ceremonies embody ethnographies that are extremely important for the nation's way of life, the formation of which goes back to the distant past. They are the tools that shape the Uzbek principles of solidarity and assistance. Weddings are mostly performed in a traditional way. During the wedding ceremonies, the social relations of society are regulated, in which not only a new family is built, but also a bond of solidarity among the related seeds, neighbours. Songs which are told during weddings (in some regions mostly folk epics sung by *bakhshi (baxshi) particularly in Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya*), however, raise the spirit of the ceremony and enhance cultural significance. Particularly, wedding ceremonies in Uzbek people consist of a series of events held in sequence, with the variety of customs and national decorations in the cross section of provinces, cities, as well as unique with *lapar, yor-yor* and examples of folk oral creativity (*dostonlar*), which are said when conducting each of them [5]. For example, *kelin salom (the bridal salute)* is one of the most ancient and popular wedding ceremonies of Uzbek people. This ethnography is associated with the bride's entry into a new family, in which the bride salutes the older representatives or relatives of the family, while the assembled guests present gifts to the new bride. This ceremony shows the importance of respect and attention among people in Uzbek society.

Nikoh (marriage). This is held in different people's mainly based on religious rules. The marriage of the bride and groom is recited by the imam (*imom*), who is a representative of the religion on the basis of religious ceremonies. The marriage training ceremony is held in the bride's *maiden dress (oq libos - mainly a dress made of white fabric)*, which is an important step in the wedding [6].

To'yona. Gifts or money brought by guests, this is a ceremony that has existed for a long time at Uzbek weddings, and the gift brought at the wedding is often perceived as financial support. This realia reflects the traditions of the hospitality of the people and mutual assistance.

To'y korteji (wedding procession). It is an integral part of modern Uzbek weddings and marks the solemn part of the wedding. The bride's habit of going to the house and the wedding room is carried out by modern cars. In history, horse-drawn carriages were used in place of the wedding cortege.

Sep. It is part of a traditional wedding ceremony and is a collection of material funds or gifts given to the bride's side by the groom before or at the wedding of the bride and groom. It is often given as a tribute to the bride's family. The contents of *sep* can mainly contain coins, valuables, clothing, household items, jewelry, and other valuable gifts.

In English society, both wedding ceremonies have historical roots, and their national traditions are preserved. They are often based on religious rules and royal traditions.

White wedding (*oq libos*). This is one of the traditions that is the most important in English weddings. The white dress is a symbol of purity and innocence in marriage and has been preserved since the 19th century.

The Bridal bouquet. The bridal bouquet is a beautiful tradition that began during the ancient Roman period, when brides carry herbs and flowers as symbols of fertility, prosperity and good luck. Today it is a symbol of love, beauty and the beginning of a new life. At English weddings, roses, lilies and orchids are simple flowers in a bouquet. Another tradition associated with this reality is to shoot a bouquet, where the bride throws her bouquet into a group of unmarried girls. It is believed that the woman who caught the bouquet will get married next.

In Russian people, too, there were historical peculiarities of processions and wedding ceremonies, and even words, songs in a special speech mold were used. For example, the symbolic oratory molds used by suitors were usually enriched with humor and symbols. For example: “*Мы к вам с добром, вы к нам с пирогом*” meaning “*We have come with good, and you meet us with a pie*” while “*Руки и сердца просим*” – was used as a symbol of asking for the bride's hand and heart on behalf of the groom. While the colloquial molds used in Russian wedding ceremonies use the phrase “*Бога благослови*” (May God help you) for the purpose of Wishing well-being, peace and happiness in a wedding according to its religious-spiritual content, “*На здоровье!*” is used to mean wishing health, good to those gathered when wedding food and sweets are served.

It is difficult to imagine the social way of life of each nation without words and phrases that express rituals and those that express condolences and sympathy, just as we could not imagine without wedding ceremonies and celebrations. As a result of the dramatic escalation of disasters, wars and conflicts, which are generally observed all over the earth, different nations have to face various tragedies and sorrows. As a result of this, the category of condolences is in turn being renewed. In this regard, the issue of a new interpretation of the linguistic features of the words on this topic is of particular relevance, and we found it necessary to dwell on the role of ethnography and national realities in their reflection and give examples of them. “*Condolences are the sum of all words and phrases that can be applied to express sympathy for someone*” [7]. Through these words, human beings use words and phrases that encourage people to be patient and encouraging in each other's difficult days. Although this process differs from one another in terms of form based on different traditions and religious views of different people, it can be said that they have one common meaning. That is, the main goal of the concept of condolence is to comfort people, encourage them, call for patience and relieve resentment.

In interethnic relations, the bowing person communicates and uses certain types of rituals, taking into account the culture and values of the azador. For example, in Uzbeks, the culture of condolence has been formed over the centuries, which is articulated in a way that is more integrated into the religion of Islam and the views associated with it. The following words of condolence are used when attending the funeral. “*Alloh sabr bersin!*”, “*Joyi jannatdan bo 'lsin*”, “*Hamdardmiz*”, “*Qabri nurga to 'lsin*” “*Oxirati obod bo 'lsin*”. These phrases are aimed at fulfilling the task of providing spiritual comfort to the loved ones of the deceased. The religious lexicon in which these phrases are used (e.g. “*paradise*”(jannat), “*end*” (oxirat) “*tomb*” (qabr), “*patience*” (sabr) [8] are common to Muslim people and show the influence of Islamic culture. In addition, Uzbeks have a tradition of helping neighbors or relatives with food.

This situation, of course, is not alien to the British either. In English, condolences are often associated with personal empathy according to English culture, in addition to verbatim expression. Phrases will mainly be directed to respect the personal pain, trouble and sadness of people. It is also common to offer condolences by phone calling or messaging. Unlike some other cultures, British mourning and customs tend to emphasize privacy and personal space, allowing the

bereaved to grieve in their own way. Here are some condolence phrases which are common for English people and their meanings:

Table 1

English phrase	Meaning/Usage	Uzbek translation
<i>I am sorry for your loss</i>	General expression of sympathy	Siz uchun afsusdaman
<i>May they rest in peace</i>	A respectful phrase for the deceased	Joyi jannatda bo'lsin
<i>You are in my thoughts and prayers</i>	Expressing ongoing support and sympathy	Siz doim mening duolarimasiz
<i>My deepest condolences</i>	A formal way to express sorrowness	Chin dildan hamdardlik bildiraman
<i>I am sorry to hear about tragic death of your father</i>	More personal way of expressing sympathy	Otangizning fojeali o'limi haqida eshitganimdan afsusdaman
<i>I really like to be a witness of your happiness</i>	Offers hopeful support for the future	Men yana qayta sizning baxtingizga guvoh bo'lishni istardim [9]

In Russians, however, condolences are associated with orthodox traditions. In such cases, the following phrases are used: “Примите мои соболезнования”, “Царство ему небесное”, “Мы скорбим вместе с вами”, “Пусть земля ему будет пухом”. In Russian culture, along with religious factors, great attention is paid to honoring the memory of the deceased. There is also a custom in Russians to make a *венки* with flowers and a black ribbon at the time of Bow [10].

In addition, it is very common for Russians who live in some parts of Russia to observe a *nine-day* (*девятый день*) and *forty-day* (*сороковой день*) mourning period, during which *memorial gatherings* (*поминки*) are held. They typically include a meal with symbolic dishes such as *кутья* (*сладкая пшеничная каша*) and *блины*, which are shared among family, relatives and friends to honor the deceased. Visiting the cemetery on particular dates, such as *Радоница* (*a special day of remembrance in the Orthodox tradition*), is also a deeply rooted tradition for Russian people.

REFERENCES

1. Avezov, Muxtar. (1992). *The Role of Weddings in Alpomish and Other Central Asian Epics*. -Tashkent: 56-60-bet.
2. Bromberg, M. (2000). *1100 Words You Need to Know*. - New York: Barron's Educational Series, Inc, 337 p.
3. Ivanova, N.A. (1998). *Russkiy obryadovyy folklor*. - Moscow: Izdatelstvo “Nauka”, p. 143.
4. Mahmudov, A. (1926). *O'zbek xalqining diniy va ma'daniy an'analari*. - Toshkent: Sharq, p. 356.
5. Narmurodova, G. (2024). *Ingliz va o'zbek tillarida ta'ziya nutqining lingvomadaniy xususiyatlari [Matn]: monografiya*. - Toshkent: Bookmany print, p. 132.
6. Shanskiy, N.M. (1976). *Russkaya leksikografiya*. - Moscow: Nauka, p. 33.
7. Superanskaya, A.V. (1976). *Obshchaya teoriya imeni sobstvennogo*. - Moscow: Nauka, p. 89.
8. Vereshchagin, E.M., & Kostomarov, V.G. (1976). *Yazyk i kultura*. - Moscow: Nauka, p. 45.